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Editorial

The God Who Is Present Everywhere

Ancient texts that may seem nonsensical and ludicrous to many people today have been explored by humanity in its quest for meaning and the truth. In an effort to uncover deeper truths, we find ourselves attempting to extrapolate symbolic meaning from these stories. In this essay, we set out on a quest to uncover the scientific knowledge buried within these myths, piecing together a map that converts religious discourse into a profound science, pointing us in the direction of a comprehension of God.

A mountain with enormous significance in many mythologies, Meru, is one of the main myths we examine. Its descriptions are so improbable and inconsistent. So we are left to wonder if it really is a mountain. We explore the concept that Meru signifies a structure within us rather than an outside mountain, opening up a secret realm within.

The author methodically analyses the mythologies, from Earth's location to the functions of gods like Garuda and

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Vayu deva, in order to highlight the similarities between the texts and the interior structure of the human body. Every detail, no matter how mystical, starts to line up with scientific understanding, causing us to realise that the entirety of religious teachings is contained within each and every one of us.

By digging deeper, the author uncovers the nature of the underworld, Hell, and Heaven and elucidates how they reflect in our own landscape. The Milky Ocean's churning, an apparently fantastical story, turns out to be a profound process that reflects our biological reality.

The author is faced with inquiries regarding the many gods and goddesses amid these revelations. The likes of Brahma, Vishnu, Shiva, Durga, Kaali, and others are viewed not just as deities but as metaphors for various facets of the complex operation of the human body. Our internal cosmos is fabricated from the threads of their stories.

The author illustrates that the universe is inside us, as recent discoveries made by science bridges the gap between empirical logic and mysticism. From the scriptures of all religions, which come together as part of one big religion, we discover the road that the soul must take in order to escape the never-ending flames of Hell.

This article is a profound invitation to see how science and religion combine to form a beautiful synergy and how what at first seems mythological can in actuality be meaningful and true. We unlock the door to an enlightened view on the cosmos, ourselves, and the divine by comprehending the subtle relationships between our internal anatomy and the classical stories.

The Editor

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Rama Inside and the God Outside: Searching for All Inclusive and Compassionate God

Omnist Ainarihc

Independent Researcher

Abstract: For us human beings, two of our central most preoccupations are to understand the origin of the universe and the afterlife. Both are, in a way connected with God. However, with it, there are several other questions intertwined, like free will, fate, morality, sins, justice, consciousness and the nature of this universe.

On one hand science strives to solve these riddles through logic, reasoning, and universal laws. It has a lesser place for God, faith, morality and consciousness and a higher place for accidents, probabilities and equations. Science has no place for abstract unprovable concepts such as hell and heaven. But when the stakes are so high, we can't rely upon the absence of a proof of God because in reality, at death's door is where even the jurisdiction of science ends.

On the other hand, we have various religious scriptures that talk about the presence of God, hell, heaven, soul, divine justice and even stories

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pertaining to the creation of the universe. But it appears to lack reason and logic. Everything in the religious scriptures seems so fantastical that scriptures are either called mythology, or contradictory or both. The point where we are at now, we can't rely on something that is considered a myth, something that seems to be absurd, illogical and self-contradictory.

This paper attempts to prove that all religions follow the same God and that what appears to look like nothing more than brilliant works of imagination written by spiritual masters who had very little or no understanding of modern science to actually be science of the highest order. Everything written in the different religious scriptures is absolutely and precisely true, and is in reality, part of a larger science that finally leads to God. This paper tries to be the bridge between the most advanced science and the deep transcendental religions.

Keywords: Mount Meru, Rama, God, Kurm, Kali, Earth, Varaha

Introduction

The scriptures are full of stories that seem illogical or self-contradictory to the point of absurdity. In an attempt to find meaning we tend to extricate a symbolic meaning out of it when there is none. Why does Brahma sit on Lotus? Why did he come out of Vishnu's navel? Why was Vishnu in human form? Why did Jesus walk on water?

This paper, with help of fragments from different scriptures deciphers the scientific information hidden in them and lays out a blueprint through which the entire religious discourse could be turned into a profound science that leads to God.

This paper talks about the various myths of Meru, which couldn't have been proved to be true in any other way and which in turn proves every single thing to be scientific. This paper explains the mythical descriptions of Garuda (Kite), the eternal fires of Hell, Heaven, the concentric Nether world

(Patala), Earth on Shesha-Naga, Kurm, Varah's tusks and the churning of the Milky ocean.

Finally, as a final note, the paper deciphers the path that the soul should take to avoid the eternal fires of Hell.

1. Myths of Mount Meru

Meru is an essential figure in several mythologies. From its structures, to its size, to its presence in several wars. Its position relative to Hell makes it pivotal in finding the location of Hell. If Meru can be found, Hell can be found. If hell exists, then so does heaven, and so does God.

1. What's written about Meru in the Brahma Purana, makes us question everything about Meru as a real mountain. It's written that Meru lies in the center of the universe. It is so huge that the whole universe lies along its axis. However, we don't see any astronomically huge mountain around. Therefore, all the stories that are tied to Meru have become myths.
2. We know that Earth is spherical, but the scriptures say that the Earth buds out from the top of meru, like the sepal of a flower. Besides this, Meru is part of many other stories, but the information in them appears contradictory at first glance. For example, earth lies on the hood of snake Shesha-naga, earth lies on the back of Kurm Avatara, earth is the butt of Goddess Shakti. How could all of them be true, when not even one of them seems true?
3. Jambu Dweep, Brahma-loka, lies on the top of Meru. If earth buds out from the top of Meru, how can Brahma loka also lie on the top of it? Contradictory and meaningless.

4. During a fight With Vayu deva, Vayu deva destroyed the north end of mount Meru. Even if We don't consider the meaning of directions in space, how could a mountain be involved in a fight? Is it conscious? At the same time, touch is considered as the virtue of Vayu deva. Why?

5. During this fight. Garuda, a kite-like bird, saved Meru. Now if everything about Meru is true, if everything written in religions is true, everything about this bird-like creature, Garuda must also be

true. With every other character introduced, the probability of impossible events becoming true gets even smaller.

6. Meru is so gigantic that even the sun revolves around Meru from north to south. Even if we were to leave the solar system out, it contradicts the basic definition of directions. Sun, even relatively, must move from east to west. Again, not one single information follows any logic. How could all of them be true?

7. Meru is held up by Vayu deva on three pillars. Why three? And does he always hold Meru on three pillars?

8. Goddess Durga holds Meru like a Veena. Does she always hold it? Do Vayu deva and Durga hold Meru at the same time?

9. Meru is fibrous. With all the mythological stories involving wars and Gods, this information was not necessary. It seems to serve no purpose. Just like Vayu-deva and Goddess Durga holding Meru at the same time.

Meru is so gigantic that even the sun revolves around Meru from north to south. Even if we were to leave the solar system out, it contradicts the basic definition of directions. Sun, even relatively, must move from east to west. Again, not one single information follows any logic.

10. Beneath Meru lies the netherworld, Patala-loka. From here, everything about the netherworld has to be true.
11. Parallel to the netherworld lies Hell. For Hell to exist, for justice to exist, for God to exist, everything written above must be absolutely true.
12. River Ganges falls on Meru and splits into four. We know the whole path of Ganges and there is no mountain that huge that splits the river into four.

At this point it is important to bring into consideration those who wrote the scriptures. If they were enlightened beings why would they write something that contradicted itself or lacked basic knowledge. Or could it be that what they wrote was truth, as is. But then if it's the truth why can't we find it? Because we have been looking in the wrong place. The universe that religions talks about lies within us. All the stories, all the characters, from Rama to Jesus, lie within every one of us.

The Truth of Mount Meru

It might appear to be symbolic, but our back bone is called Meru dand. Dand means stick. What if it's the stick attached to Meru, somewhere between medulla oblongata?

- If we consider the human body as the real universe then the whole universe lies along the axis of medulla oblongata.
- From the top of medulla oblongata, the cerebral cortex appears to be budding out, like a flower. Could the cerebral cortex be earth?

Fig: Medulla oblongata (Gigantocellular reticular formation at the center is Meru)

Source : Iordanova R, Reddivari AKR. Neuroanatomy, Medulla Oblongata. [Updated 2022 Jul 25]. In: StatPearls [Internet]. Treasure Island (FL): StatPearls Publishing; 2023 Jan-. [Figure, The Hind-brain or Rhombencephalon, Upper...] Available from: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK551589/figure/article-24901.image.f2>

- Other mountains, cerebral peduncles, support reticular formation just like buttresses.
- Now, the virtue of Vayu deva being touch seems useless and so did him destroying the north corner of Meru. And so does Vayu deva lifting Meru specifically on three pillars. Why three, why Vayu deva? Does he always hold Meru on

those pillars? It seems irrelevant, mythical, but it's the naked truth, as seen. Somatosensory neurons pass through the left (north) of the medulla oblongata. And is held up by it on three pillars.

From the top of medulla oblongata, the cerebral cortex appears to be budding out, like a flower. Could the cerebral cortex be earth?

Modified Fig: Cortico-spinal tract

Source : Figure 2. Corticospinal tract conveying motor signals from motor cortex to skeletal muscles. The motor cortex and corticospinal tracts degenerate in ALS.

Studies on metals in motor neuron disease - Scientific Figure on ResearchGate. Available from:

https://www.researchgate.net/figure/Corticospinal-tract-blue-conveying-motor-signals-from-motor-cortex-to-skeletal-muscles_fig1_237008975 [accessed 22 May, 2023]

- On the top of medulla oblongata lies the mesencephalon. If mesencephalon is Garuda (kite), it must have a snake in its beak and feet and also a nectar pot in its hand, specifically in the Anjani mudra (joined hands).

If mesencephalon is Garuda (kite), it must have a snake in its beak and feet and also a nectar pot in its hand, specifically in the Anjani mudra (joined hands).

Mesencephalon has oculo-motor nerve and trochlear nerve that looks like snake in beak and feet. Optic radiations look like its wings, [Brian A. Wandell, Jonathan Winawer, fig-10, 2011]. Pituitary gland looks like a pot in its hands. But here starts another chain of events. If pituitary is nectar pot, there must have been a churning of the milky ocean. Therefore, there must be a **kurm avatara**.

(Modified) Mesencephalon (Garuda) with nectar pot (pituitary gland) in its hands (optic tract)

Source : Brian A. Wandell, Jonathan Winawer, Imaging retinotopic maps in the human brain, Vision Research, Volume 51, Issue 7, 2011, Fig. 10. Optic radiation in the human brain. Available from: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0042698910003780> (25)

(Modified) Mesencephalon (Garuda), optic radiations(Wings) and trochlear nerve (Snake) Sources : [Henry Vandyke Carter](#), [Henry Gray](#) (1918) *Anatomy of the Human Body* [Gray's Anatomy](#), [Plate 719](#).

Fig Hind- and mid-brains; postero-lateral view. Available from: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Trochlear_nerve#/media/File:Gray719.png Brian A. Wandell, Jonathan Winawer, Imaging retinotopic maps in the human brain, Vision Research, Volume 51, Issue 7, 2011, Fig. 10. Optic

radiation in the human brain. Available from: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0042698910003780> [25]

- Even if we assume that the sun that is revolving around Meru, it must have been written as east to west. Writing that the sun revolves around Meru from north to south seems to lack basic knowledge of reality. Also, it is written that the sushumna nadi is one of solar radiations. That also infers that solar radiations within us. In another description of Garuda (kite) said that its wings shine the sun. Why not forehead or face?

Now keeping in mind that Surya nadi lies just beneath the eye, could it mean one of our eyes could be considered Surya? Optic tract moves around Meru from left to right (north to south). That would mean from an internal perspective that the sun does revolve around Meru from North to South.

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Now keeping in mind that Surya nadi lies just beneath the eye, could it mean one of our eyes could be considered Surya? Optic tract moves around Meru from left to right (north to south). That would mean from an internal perspective that the sun does revolve around Meru from North to South.

- If optic fibers represent solar rays, then there must be a connection between Garuda (mesencephalon) and Optic fibers (solar radiations). Optic Radiations do look like wings of mesencephalon, Garuda.

- Medulla oblongata(Gigantocellular-reticular formation) (Meru) is fibrous in nature.

2. Nether-World

1. If Meru is Medulla oblongata, there must be a concentric netherworld beneath it. The layers in the order, Black, white, Yellow, red, hard stone, and golden. It seems like a fantasy, because no world could be of just one color. And between all these colors why is a hard layer mentioned? It could conveniently have been chosen as another color.
2. Again, a snake (vasuki), passes through the middle of this concentric world. Why a snake? And how?
3. Thousands of snakes bite the larger snake (Shesh-Naga) precisely like a plough holding a hammer in their hands. This seems absurd and mythical. What do they do with that hammer? And how are snakes even holding anything?
4. These snakes sprawl through the entire universe. We don't see any such snakes sprawling around our universe.

The Truth of Nether world

- Beneath medulla oblongata lies the spinal cord. The spinal cord consists of concentric layers called meninges. The

- layers are in the order, gray matter, white matter, yellow epidural layer, red veins(epidural layer) [1], then hard bone and finally golden ligamenta flava [2].
- How can the order of colors be the same? With each information that is proved to be true, the probability of the information provided in the scriptures being mythical or these correlations being a coincidence becomes less and less. It must be observed that the order of colors and a presence of a hard layer justify the netherworld to be the Spinal cord.
 - If spinal cord is Nether world then there must be a snake Vasuki/Shesha-naga passing through the middle of it. Cingulate Gyrus + hypothalamus + parasympathetic/sympathetic nervous system is the snake Vasuki. Cingulate Gyrus [3] and Hypothalamus [4, 5] plays key role in regulating autonomic nervous system (Sympathetic/Parasympathetic nervous system)

Fig: Cingulate Gyrus, (hood of the snake) + Hypothalamus + parasympathetic/ sympathetic nervous system (Tail of the snake)

Source: Jumah FR, Dossani RH. Neuroanatomy, Cingulate Cortex. [Updated 2022 Dec 6]. In: StatPearls [Internet]. Treasure Island (FL): StatPearls Publishing; 2023 Jan-. [Figure, Cingulate gyrus. Image courtesy S Bhimji MD] Available from:

<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK537077/figure/article-19561.image.f3/>

- If the limbic lobe + hypothalamus + parasympathetic / sympathetic nervous system is Vasuki. Then there must be thousands of snakes biting it like a plough holding a hammer in their hand. In the image below it can be seen how the neurons dig into the parasympathetic / sympathetic nervous system like a plough and the ganglions are the hammer that they hold.

Fig: (Modified) Sympathetic ganglion (hammer in snake's hand)

Source: Figure 1. Nerve impulse pathway to the sympathetic ganglion.

Current treatment options for craniofacial hyperhidrosis - Scientific Figure on ResearchGate. Available from: https://www.researchgate.net/figure/Nerve-impulse-pathway-to-the-sympathetic-ganglion_fig1_346941020 [accessed 9 Apr, 2023]

- These snakes are spread across the entire universe. Do we see any such snakes outside? No. But if we turn inwards then the entire universe is sprawling with these snakes i.e. neurons, the nervous system.

On judgment day, these snakes spew venom and turn the entire universe into hell.

3. Churning of the Milky Ocean

The churning of the milky ocean may seem like an outlandish tale, full of myths, contradictions and irrelevant information.

1. The churning of the milky ocean produced a number of things, but the two major products were Hallahal and amrita. Hallahal poison, when it came out of the churning, could have destroyed the entire universe. How? Why did it not start destroying the universe from where it was before the churning?

2. Amrita, the nectar came out of the churning at the very end. The Gods drank the Amrita and became immortal. Where are those Gods now?
3. For this event, lord Vishnu took the form of Kurm (tortoise). Because tortoises have a hard shell. But, is this it? Is it the hardest thing God could create, a tortoise's shell? Had there been a mention of a highly dense material, it would have been more believable.
4. Even if it is believed that God turned himself into a tortoise. The way he turned into a tortoise seems irrelevant as well. He took form out of a soft case. Why?
5. To churn the ocean, mount mandara was to be kept on the tortoise's back. But strangely, even unnecessarily, mount Mandara rose from between the tortoise's knees, passing through its back as if there's a hole in it.
6. Mount Mandara lies to the east of Meru. In hyperspace, east –west doesn't mean anything.
7. Kurm is said to carry earth on its back. The same earth that buds out of Meru. The same earth that is kept on the Shesha Naga's hood.
8. One piece of information doesn't seem to make any sense at all. Vayu deva(wind) is responsible for closing the eye that passes through Kurm.
9. Kurm shaligram(Holy stone of kurm), is said to be elevated from the east. How could a tortoise be elevated from the east? Does it not move? And a tortoise is not elevated in any direction at all. Why was there a necessity of mentioning a symbol that doesn't look like a tortoise.
10. Kurmasana doesn't look like a tortoise. In kurm asana, the front limbs go backwards and the rear limbs come forward.

We know this is not how a tortoise looks like. Again, what is the necessity of naming an asana after Kurm when it doesn't look like it?

11. Another symbol of Kurm is grass on the surface of brick.

Now, there are three different symbols of Kurm and all of them have to be true.

12. Kurm is in the east facing west.

13. Another riddle that is almost impossible to resolve is the orientation of Kurm, Varaha and Shesha. According to

some versions, Earth lies on the back of Kurm. Other versions mention that earth

lies on the hood of Shesha. And some versions say earth

lies on the tusks of Varaha. How could all of them be true? And, it is also said that Varaha has one leg on Kurm

and another on the hood of

Shesha. So where is this earth that is on shesha's hood, kurm's back, and also Varaha's tusk? Where are the feet of Varaha? It might be said that even for a myth it was not well thought of.

So where is this earth that is on shesha's hood, kurm's back, and also Varaha's tusk? Where are the feet of Varaha? It might be said that even for a myth it was not well thought of.

If Meru is medulla oblongata, spinal cord is patala loka, then with all those precisions, there must be a Kurm in spite of all the improbabilities and contradictions.

4. Kurm

1. Garuda (mesencephalon) holds Pituitary gland like a nectar pot.
For everything to be true, Pituitary must be the nectar pot.

(Modified) Mesencephalon (Garuda) with nectar pot (pituitary gland) in its hands (optic tract)

Source: Brian A. Wandell, Jonathan Winawer, Imaging retinotopic maps in the human brain, *Vision Research*, Volume 51, Issue 7, 2011, Fig. 10. Optic radiation in the human brain. Available from:

<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0042698910003780> [25]

2. God became a tortoise because the Sphenoid body looks like a turtle. Below is the image of a sphenoid body.

Fig: Sphenoid bone (Kurm) carrying Pituitary gland (Nectar pot)
Source: The 360 photography: a new anatomical insight of the sphenoid bone. Interest for anatomy teaching and skull base surgery - Scientific Figure on ResearchGate. Available from:
https://www.researchgate.net/figure/Photography-Anterior-view-of-the-sphenoid-bone-This-anterior-view-shows-the-global_fig3_303769896
[accessed 24 May, 2023]

Fig: Photography. Anterior view of the sphenoid bone. This anterior view shows the global aspect of the sphenoid bone from a trans-nasal approach with its bone sinus, nose, eyes, wings and pterygoid plates

3. Sphenoid looks like a Shaligram (holy stone), elevated from the east (anterior).
4. Kurm asana doesn't look like a tortoise but does look like a sphenoid body.

Sphenoid looks like a Shaligram (holy stone), elevated from the east (anterior).

5.

Kurm Asana (tortoise pose)

Source: Gabriella giubilaro, [Oct 12 2015], [Photograph], [Online].

Available from: <https://www.yogajournal.com/poses/4-steps-master-tortoise-pose-kurmasana/> [accessed on 22 May 2023]

Fig: Sphenoid body

6. Mandara rising from between the knees, through its back seems irrelevant. But it's exactly the way the Rathke's pouch raises through developing sphenoid body to form pituitary gland. [\[6, 7, 8\]](#)

7. Vayu (wind) closing the eyes is said to pass through the Kurm. It seems meaningless. But it's the oculo-motor nerve (required for closing the eyes) passing through the sphenoid body.

Source: Fig 3, Adrian Barszszak, R.Shane tubbs, Nicol Zielinska, Lukasz Olenic,

[Annals of Anatomy - Anatomischer Anzeiger](#)
[Volume 245](#), January 2023, 152004

Clinical analysis of cavernous sinus anatomy, pathologies, diagnostics, surgical management and complications – Comprehensive review

8. Kurm nadi (internal carotid artery) is called Kurm Naadi for it passes through the sphenoid body.

Source: Fig 3, Adrian barserzak, R.Shane tubbs, Nicol zielinska, Lukasz Olenic,

[Annals of Anatomy - Anatomischer Anzeiger](#)
[Volume 245](#), January 2023, 152004

Clinical analysis of cavernous sinus anatomy, pathologies, diagnostics, surgical management and complications – Comprehensive review

9. Sphenoid body lies in the east (anterior) facing west (posterior).
10. God becoming Kurm out of a cake seemed irrelevant. But it's exactly how it happens. It's the process of osteo-genesis.
11. Brick and grass symbol seems irrelevant. Because the shell of Tortoise doesn't look like brick neither is there any grass on its top. On the other hand, the sphenoid body resembles a brick and the neurons above it look like grass. Nothing is contradictory. To best define the sphenoid body, all the three descriptions are required.
12. The same earth (cerebral cortex) that seems to buds out of Meru (Medulla oblongata) as a flower, that lies on Vasuki's hood must

also lie on Kurm's back. The following diagram proves that it does.

Fig: Sphenoid body and cerebral cortex

Source: Fig: Anatomy of the paranasal sinuses (spaces between the bones around the nose).

PDQ Adult Treatment Editorial Board. Paranasal Sinus and Nasal Cavity Cancer Treatment (Adult) (PDQ®): Patient Version. 2023 Mar 17. In: PDQ Cancer Information Summaries [Internet]. Bethesda (MD): National Cancer Institute (US); 2002-. Available from:

<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK66003/>

If Cerebral cortex is the earth there must be a Goddess of earth lying at the buttocks of Goddess Shakti. And if the cerebral cortex is Earth, then there must be a Varaha avatar that holds Earth on its tusks.

5. Earth (in Sacred Scriptures)

1. If the Parasympathetic/sympathetic nervous system is the longest snake Vasuki, then according to the scriptures, **Earth** must be on the hood of Shesha.
2. Earth should be on the back of kurm (tortoise) avatara.

3. Earth should also bud out from the top of Meru precisely like a flower.
4. This same earth must also lie on the tusks of Varaha avatara. From here, everything about Varaha must also be true.
5. Finally, for everything about the Earth from the scriptures to be true, Earth must also be on the hips of Goddess Shakti. How can earth be in all these places?

The Truth about Earth

- The cerebral cortex is the Earth mentioned in the scriptures and it lies above the Parasympathetic/sympathetic nervous system same as the Earth lies on the hood of Shesha.
- The cerebral cortex, Earth, also lies above the sphenoid body, Kurm avatara.

Modified image. Shesh-Naga (cingulate Gyrus) carrying the earth(cerebral cortex) on its hood.

- The earth that scriptures talk about buds out of the top of Meru. If Medulla oblongata is Meru, then the cerebral cortex must be the earth.

Modified Fig: The Telencephalon (First vesicle) [9]

- The Earth must lie on the tusks of Varaha. And Varaha must pull it out of water while it was sinking because of its own water.

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From Meru to the netherworld to Kurma to earth, everything that seems irrelevant, mythical, contradictory is actually the truth, as observed. From this we can conclude that there also exists hell, running parallel to Patala loka.

Meru to the netherworld to Kurma to earth, everything seems irrelevant, mythical, contradictory is actually the as observed. From this we conclude that there also hell, running parallel to loka. The digestive tract. At of death, the soul comes out Mooladhara chakra and rises. the blood drops from 7.4 to after death [10]. This makes body burning hell for soul. If

the soul enters the tempting gate that leads to the digestive tract then it burns in a timeless hell for eternity, witnessing the rain of fire and blood.

A nonscientific photograph to give an idea of what soul passes through after death for centuries (inside)

Shiva, Brahma, Vishnu, Revelations in Bible, the Saraswati River, Ganges, Kaali, Kaal ratri, Kubera, Jesus, the Pyramids and other monuments, dead sea, mosques and temples of all religions that the soul would witness if it were to go through the path of temples, and Plato's real world are discussed in another article.

6. Rama Inside

Everything has to be proved true for religion to be established as an authentic science. And if despite all the contradictions, all the illogical stories, everything comes out to be true then it must be believed that the nature of the universe and heaven is as written in the religious scriptures. Science has a major role to play in understanding it. Had science not been there, it would have been impossible to explain the minute subtleties. From the microscopic to the geographic, it is explicable because of science. Science is the bridge between our logic seeking brains and God.

We find the meaning of the monuments and deciphers the map of the inner realm and illuminates the path that the soul is supposed to follow if it takes the path of temples and mosques.

Another doubt that comes to mind is that if there is only one God, how come there are so many religions? And why did the Gods not create one religion? This article proves that all religions are part of one great religion.

Another doubt that makes us skeptical about religion is the reasons for which God performed the miracles he did. Why did he only do what he did? This article answers that too.

This article also finds the meaning of the monuments and deciphers the map of the inner realm and illuminates the path that the soul is supposed to follow if it takes the path of temples and mosques.

7. Gods

If Meru is the Medulla oblongata and the limbic system and parasympathetic nervous/ sympathetic nervous system is the Shesha, there has to be a Brahma and a Vishnu in between, everything as documented. There must be Lord Shiva, Goddess Shakti, Goddess Parvati, Goddess Kaali, Goddess Durga, and the one most critical to understanding the nature of the universe, Varaha.

The Origin

The creation of the Universe is the greatest point of debate between sciences and religions. According to science there probably was a Big Bang, that led to the universe we now live in. On the other hand, is religion telling us various utterly fantastical tales of the Origin. One of the major causes of disbelief is that all religions tell different stories about the origin, and none of them appear to be logical. Even if one of them were to be true, the rest of them seem like myths. How could all of them be true?

1. According to the scriptures, a lotus came out of Lord Vishnu's Navel and Lord Brahma sat atop that lotus. Lord Brahma then created the rest of the universe. This seems completely mythical. Why and how did a lotus come

before anything else in the universe? And why did lord Brahma sit on a lotus rather than on a throne? Does he ever get up from there? Does he get bored or tired of sitting on lotus? Most importantly, who created lord Vishnu?

2. While lord Brahma was trying to come out of lord Vishnu, Lord Vishnu sealed all his holes. Brahma found one hole, the navel of lord Vishnu and came out of it. This seems unnecessary and irrelevant. The story was already unbelievable to begin with.
3. Even more strangely, there is a lake in the stem of the lotus that lord Brahma sits upon. The lake is called Saraswati-kund. How could there be a lake inside a stem? It does not end there.
4. The chain of seemingly illogical and irrelevant stories continue, making it more and more improbable, unless it is absolutely true. It is specifically mentioned that there is a stump in the middle of this lake, called sthanu-vatt. Why a stump? It is said that when the soul reaches this stump, it finds moksha.
5. This same Saraswati-kund is said to be in Kedarnath, from whence the Saraswati river flows. We don't see a Saraswati river in kedarnath, nor any sthanu-vatt. How could the same lake be inside the stem of a lotus as well as in Kedarnath when there isn't a single lake in Kedarnath. From here, the chain of myths find another link. River Saraswati is said to be the ladder to heaven. If everything is true, so must the Saraswati River and all its myths.
6. In the east of this lake lies the hip shaped Indra.

7. And in the west lie lord Shiva and Parvati. The chain of myths finds yet another link.

River Saraswati is said to be the ladder to heaven. If everything is true, so must the Saraswati River and all its myths.

The Truth about Gods

- Between Meru and Shesha lies Jambu-dweep, the abode of Lord Brahma. And Lord Brahma must come out of Vishnu's navel. Between the Midbrain and limbic system lies the Thalamus.
- During fetal development, Cells destined to form the medial thalamic nuclei originate in the matrix layer surrounding the third ventricle. From the matrix, cells migrate to form the different nuclei [\[11\]](#), in the same way lord Brahma's lotus is said to buds out of lord Vishnu's navel. Lord brahma as looking for a hole to come out of lord Vishnu, and finally came out of his naval. Matrix layer surrounding the third ventricle is the naval of lateral thalamus (lord Vishnu)

Fig: Medial thalamus (Lord Brahma) development from thalamic gliopithilium and ependymal (naval of Lord Vishnu.)

Source: Source: Shirley A. Bayer, Joseph Altman. The Human Brain during the Second Trimester. p. 17.

- If the whole thalamus is composed of Vishnu, Brahma and the lotus, there must be a lake inside the stem of the lotus. That lake is the third ventricle.
- If the third ventricle is the lake, there must be a stump in the middle of the lake, which there is, the Interthalamic connection.

If the whole thalamus is composed of Vishnu, Brahma and the lotus, there must be a lake inside the stem of the lotus. That lake is the third ventricle.

Fig: Thalamic nuclei [12, 13]

Medial Thalamus is Lord Brahma. Ventral Thalamus is Lord Vishnu. Third ventricle is the lake in brahma's Lotus stem. Interthalamic connection is the pillar in the middle of the lake (Sthanu-vat, place here soul find liberation.)

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- If the third ventricle is the lake, Saraswati kund, there must be a hip shaped lord Indra in the east of it and Shiva and Parvati to the west. Saraswati must go to Patala from between these two. It can't be a coincidence that the hip shaped Nucleus of Accumbens lies in the anterior of it and the third eye, the virtue of lord Shiva, the pineal gland lies in the posterior of it. CSF goes to the spine through central aqueduct from between these two.

(On its way to Patala, Saraswati River must find an ocean which drinks its water through a pinhole. Saraswati River is the ladder to heaven. If one could find this river after waking up at muladhara chakra, he would find heaven. More information about Saraswati and their proofs have been explained in the book *The Grand Scheme*.)

- 1 Beneath Shiva-linga is Parvati surrounding it
- 2 Beneath pineal Gland lies habenular trigone [14]

[Source: [Christina Loukopoulou](#), [no date]. Habenula [online]. Available from: [It can't be a coincidence that the hip shaped Nucleus of Accumben lies in the anterior of it and the third eye, the virtue of lord Shiva, the pineal gland lies in the posterior of it.](https://www.kenhub.com/thumbor/lqZhUM6zHy-kdkMgicYVat336_4=/fit-in/680x680/filters:fill(FFFFFF,true):watermark(/images/watermark_only.png,0,0,0):watermark(/images/logo_url.png,-10,-10,0):format(jpeg)/images/anatomy_term/trigunum-</p>
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Fig: Ventricular system (flow of Sarasvati, the river that takes soul to heaven) Source: Michael Schuenke[no date], Fig ventricular system [online], available from: <https://doctorlib.info/anatomy/atlas-anatomy/13.html> (Churches, mosques, temples and beautiful landmarks and gods and goddesses that soul witnesses during its thousands of years of its journey to within, that

- are mentioned in the religious texts, like the revelations and many more, are explained in the book the Grand scheme written by the author of this article)
- There are a lot of stories about all the Gods because these organs are at the center of a lot of biochemistry of the human body.

If the pineal gland is Lord Shiva, and habenular nuclei are Goddess Parvati, then there must be a goddess Kaali too. Could everything written about Goddess Kaali come out to be right too?

8. Goddess Kaali

1. When goddess Parvati was furious with lord Shiva she shed her dark skin. The dark skin took form to become Goddess kaali.
2. Goddess kaali looks like a blue tongue. There seems no reason for that. This description couldn't be justified, just like Indra's being hip shaped.
3. Goddess kaali, who looks like a blue tongue, is a cluster of precisely seven tongues. How could a Goddess be a cluster of seven tongues? Why was it necessary to mention this particularly?
4. Goddess kaali stays in a triangular Yantra. Why triangular? And what does this staying in a yantra mean?
5. In another story, Kaali is said to have come out of goddess Durga, who is holding Meru like a Veena. This fixes Goddess kaali's two origins, two positions, and two structure virtues.
6. Goddess Parvati shed her skin in the Arunachal hills.

The Truth about Goddess Kaali

- IPN neurons were generated in the proximity of the ventricular surface near the confluence of the 3rd ventricle and cerebral aqueduct, migrated ventrally along the midline and then spread laterally after reaching the ventral midbrain.[\[15\]](#)
- It looks like a tongue. It consists of precisely seven tongues. [\[16\]](#)
- It lies in a triangular region in interpeduncular fossa, Posterior Perforated Substance in the midbrain. [\[17\]](#)
- IPN lies close to Median and Dorsal Raphe(head of Goddess Durga). Data shows projections from Dorsal and Median Raphe to IPN. This gives an impression of IPN (Kaali) to have come out of the Dorsal and Median Raphe nuclei (Durga's head). [\[18\]](#)
- Raphe is Goddess Durga, holding Meru like a veena (reticular formation). The reticular formation can also divide into three columns. These three columns are the raphe nuclei, located in the midline of the reticular formation core, the gigantocellular reticular nuclei and the parvocellular reticular nucle. Raphe is the goddess Durga holding the other, gigantocellular column (Meru) like a veena.[\[19\]](#)

Modified image: IPN (Kali) seems to come out of Medan raphe nucleus (Durga's head)

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9. Varaha and the Nature of Universe

With each evidence provided it becomes more evident that every story that seems illogical is precisely true for the universe within. The spiritual masters who died before death and woke up within wrote everything down, precisely and accurately. They didn't mince a word, they didn't try to make it seem believable. They simply wrote down the truth as it is. That's why it seems contradictory and irrelevant. Everything is symbolic, at the same time very literal. The writings of these great masters can be interpreted in different ways, three at least, physically, intellectually and metaphysically. Everything is precisely true. But a few questions still remain. One of them being the nature of the universe.

Everything is symbolic, at the same time very literal. The writings of these great masters can be interpreted in different ways, three at least, physically, intellectually and metaphysically. Everything is precisely true. But a few questions still remain. One of them being the nature of the universe.

To understand the nature of the universe, we have to understand Varaha. Again, from origin, to purpose, to the posture that he stands in, everything written about Varaha seems impossible to explain.

1. The virtues of lord Varaha are memory, learning and fear. Why? Why is the boar chosen to have these virtues? A boar doesn't have a good memory or learning skills. And why is fear chosen to be a virtue of a God? God is never afraid.
2. According to one legend, when Narada visited Brahma loka, he found lord Varaha sitting there, on the top of Meru. The Beauty of that place has been described in detail in the Puranas. So Varaha should be at the top of Meru.

3. According to other legends, Lord Varaha came out of a Shudra, of Valmiki and an Anthill. And then his size kept growing. Why an anthill? And, why is it that in some texts it is said to be Valmiki instead? Could this be true? Varaha came out of an anthill, the size of a thumb, but then grew larger and larger until he disappeared into the clouds.
4. Shaligram, the holy stone of Varaha, doesn't look anything like a boar.
5. Varaha is said to have golden hair on his head. Why? Do they have a purpose?
6. According to one story, when earth got too heavy due to the population, it began to shed hills and began to sink in the primordial waters. At that time Varaha Avatar saved the Earth from sinking. There is no way this story could be true.
7. In another story, Asura Hirannyaksha, put the earth in the water. Now, if there was already one version of the story present, why would another version be written? At least one of them would have to be a myth. Moreover we know that none of them is possible. Neither can earth sink due to its own weight nor would any race survive after it has been submerged into water.
8. This version has several specifics too. Like, the meaning of the word Hirranyaksha. This word means golden grass. Not to mention that we have considered fibers as grass above Kurma.
9. Before Hirranyaksha submerged the earth under water, he stayed under the ocean. Why? This part seems irrelevant.
10. According to this version, lord Varaha pierced Hirranyaksha with his teeth. The story goes on, while Varaha was inside the ocean, his teeth were piercing lord Varuna (God of water) so

lord Varuna asked lord Varaha to bend his tooth. It seems illogical. How could teeth pierce into the ocean? And how does bending the tooth help?

11. Another story tells us about the time when Goddess Earth visited the Lord Varaha with her friend Ida. Now, we know that Ida is a Naadi inside us. How could a naadi inside every one of us be friends with the Earth and visit Lord Varaha, unless Earth and Varaha are inside us too?
12. This visit is crucial to deciphering the nature of the universe. During this visit, Goddess earth asked lord Varaha about the outer universe. Lord Varaha told her that he and only he, is responsible for the outer universe. Even Lord Brahma and Lord Vishnu don't know about it. He said that the outer universe is entirely his *Maya (delusion created by him)*. If somehow, everything about Varaha is demonstrated to be true, then even the claim made by him is possible as well. The entire universe could be said to be a delusion created by mighty Lord Varaha.
13. Among all these, almost impossible to solve riddles, is the riddle of the position of Lord Varaha. Lord Varaha's idol is seen carrying Earth either on his tusks or shoulder. His one foot is on Kurm's (tortoise) head and the other foot is on Shesha's head. Now since we know that one version says earth lies on Kurm's back, another says earth lies on Shesha's hood, and this one says earth lies on Varaha's tusks. How could all of them be true, including the position of Varaha? And it contradicts the information that Varaha lies on the top of Meru.
14. In another story, lord Indra pierced Emusha (boar) with arrows that pierced meru before it struck Emusha (boar). How and why?

The Truth of Lord Varaha

- Varaha's virtues are written precisely as memory, learning and fear. Inside our brain, the virtues of the Hippocampus (papez circuit) are accordingly found to be Learning, memory and fear. How could both have exactly the same virtues? [\[20\]](#)
- There are myelinated fibers, corpus collosum on what could be called the head of hippocampus, if it's seen as the boar.

Modified image

Source: FIG 1. Schematic of the extended Papez system highlighting the principal connections of the mammillary bodies.

Signal Change in the Mammillary Bodies after Perinatal Asphyxia - Scientific Figure on ResearchGate. Available from:

<https://www.researchgate.net/figure/Schematic-of-the-extended-Papez->

- Varaha sits on the top of Meru. Hippocampus could be seen as sitting above the reticular formation.
- Lord Varaha came out of an anthill, why? Why did it disappear into the clouds?

During early embryology, ammonic neurons migrate in a zig-zag manner like ants, from the ammonic neuroepithelial layer, which looks like a microscopic anthill with ammonic cells migrating radially as well as tangentially, like ants coming out of ant hill and migrating, to the ventricular zone, which is the water carrying clouds. As these ammonic neurons do this, they get bigger and bigger and take the shape of the Hippocampus, the boar. [\[21\]](#)

- Why doesn't the Shaligram (holy stone of Varaha) look like a boar, but is the symbol of Lord Varaha? Because it looks like the ring of Hippocampus.
- During development of the cerebral cortex (proven as earth before), layer six pyramidal cells, due to over production go through programmed cell death. To the tiny soul, this looks like hills falling off the surface, [\[22\]](#). It might be the time of development of Hippocampus, it holds the cortex up. Just as it is written about Varaha saving the earth from sinking into the primordial waters due to its own weight.

Fig: Cerebral cortex shown as Goddess earth sitting on Varaha's tusks (olfactory bulb).

- During the time of development of myelinated association fibers (golden grass, Hirranyaksha) they might pull down the cerebral cortex. (development of association has not been fully understood) The same association fibers might remain under the lateral ventricles, as written about the Hirranyaksha that he remained under the ocean before he submerged the earth in primordial waters.
- The same association fibers might be pierced by the fimbriae of the hippocampus, as written about Hirranyaksha being pierced by teeth of Varaha. (development of association fibers is not fully understood as yet)

A modified image.

Association fibers, probably IFOF, crossing Fimbriae (Development of these fibers is not fully understood as yet. Further study is required in this area) [23] (Source : [Yupeng Wu](#),¹ [Dandan Sun](#),² [Yong Wang](#),¹ and [Yibao Wang](#)^{1,*}2016; 10: 88. Fig 3 : In vivo fiber tractography of the IFOF on the DSI template. (A, B) The NTU-90 showed an extended pattern compared with the subject-specific results. (C, D) A consistent pattern of five segmentations was confirmed within both hemispheres of the template. L, left; R, right. Available from: https://www.frontiersin.org/files/Articles/210920/fnana-10-00088-HTML/image_m/fnana-10-00088-g003.jpg)

Fig: Hippocampus(fornix) holding boat shaped cerebral cortex on its tusks. Boat shaped cortex above fornix. Source: Shirley A. Bayer, Joseph Altman. The Human Brain During the Second Trimester. Page 13

- The same fornix lies along the lateral ventricles. As if, if not bent, the fornix might have pierced the ventricles.

A modified image. A part of Fornix of hippocampus (white) and lateral ventricle (blue) in a contact.

Source: *Kaan Yağmurlu*, **Fig. 28.11. Lateral view of the left hemisphere.** The ependyma and tapetum have been removed to expose the parts of the lateral ventricle. Available from: <https://neupsykey.com/28-fiber-dissection-of-the-brain/>
Kaan Yağmurlu, **Fig. 28.12. Lateral view of the left hemisphere.** The basal ganglia structures have been exposed in the insular area. Available from: <https://neupsykey.com/28-fiber-dissection-of-the-brain/>

- When Goddess Earth visits Varaha with Ida, is the time of development of the cerebral cortex in the presence of Ida naadi.
- During this visit, Varaha said that the whole universe is an illusion created by him. Now, we know that the hippocampus is responsible for delusions. It now seems possible that the entire universe is our hippocampus's delusion, a purpose given to us by our own subconscious.
- If everything is true for lord Varaha, then the impossible posture of Varaha with one foot on Kurm's head and the other foot on Shesha's head, with earth on all three should also be true.

1. Earth cerebral cortex on Shesha's hood (Cingulate gyrus).
2. Shesha's hood (cingulate gyrus) over Varaha (hippocampus, fornix)
3. Varaha's foot (mammillary body) on Kurm's head (sphenoid bone) (Ilie, I.R. (2020). The Pituitary Gland. In: Introduction to Endocrinology. Springer, Cham. Fig 3.1 Representation of the normal relationships of the

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4. Varaha's foot on Shesha. (unknown vagal connection of Hippocampus [24])
5. Earth (cerebral cortex) on Varaha's tusk (olfactory bulb and fornix) as well as on Kurm's back (sphenoid body). (Source: FIG 1. Schematic of the extended Papez system highlighting the principal connections of the mammillary bodies.) (Signal Change in the Mammillary Bodies after Perinatal Asphyxia - Scientific Figure on ResearchGate. Available from: https://www.researchgate.net/figure/Schematic-of-the-extended-Papez-system-highlighting-the-principal-connections-of-the_fig1_337072277 [accessed 21 May, 2023])
6. Earth (cerebral cortex) on Varaha's shoulder (amygdala)) (Source: FIG 1. Schematic of the extended Papez system highlighting the principal connections of the mammillary bodies.) (Signal Change in the Mammillary Bodies after Perinatal Asphyxia - Scientific Figure on ResearchGate. Available from: https://www.researchgate.net/figure/Schematic-of-the-extended-Papez-system-highlighting-the-principal-connections-of-the_fig1_337072277 [accessed 21 May, 2023])

Conclusion

Scientific research has a certain success rate which seems to be higher than any explanation provided by religion. Despite this, science cannot present the reasons for extremely

improbable accidental events, from Big Bang, to accumulation of particles to form a strand of D.N.A., to an organism that had desire to eat and had a desire as well as the capacity to proliferate, evolve, and survive. Believability in science comes from logic and reasoning, it has no place for blind faith. Due to the impossibility of definitively proving Hell, Heaven, justice in nature of nature, a supreme soul, science presumes that these things do not exist.

Taking the route of logical reasoning and pure rationality, if religion were looked through the prism of science, then we would see that everything written in the religious scriptures seem to be absolutely precise. It doesn't just give us a small possibility of Hell, it outright proves it. The existence of Varaha will validate that this entire world is merely an illusion and furthermore, the existence of divine justice in the very nature of the universe which further proves the existence of a divine power will be undeniable for all to see. This unique perspective only becomes possible when religion is looked at through the prism of science. Hence, when religion is explained scientifically it will be a lot simpler for the present humans to attain Moksha.

Taking the route of logical reasoning and pure rationality, if religion were looked through the prism of science, then we would see that everything written in the religious scriptures seem to be absolutely precise.

The human condition is a miserable one. We are an organism cursed and blessed with intelligence and with that intelligence comes an unending torrent of unanswered questions which plagues our very existence. Our search for truth is a never ending quest because of our own foolishness, our inability to see the fundamental truths lying right below our nose. The answers to our most harrowing questions have always been within us. This fact has been told, written and repeated countless times over the centuries but we have been too preoccupied to understand this simple fact. However, now with the advent of modern sciences the truth has been laid bare for everyone to understand. The outer science of the external world is finally at the junction where it reflects the inner science of the human mind and soul. It is only because of the advancement of science that we have been able to undeniably prove the science contained within the religious scriptures of antiquity. We have proved through this journal the immense scientific knowledge hidden with these scriptures. To all disbelievers and skeptics, the amount of evidence and correlations provided here should make it abundantly clear that what we have proved here goes beyond the realm of measly coincidences and into the

We are an organism cursed and blessed with intelligence and with that intelligence comes an unending torrent of unanswered questions which plagues our very existence. Our search for truth is a never ending quest because of our own foolishness, our inability to see the fundamental truths lying right below our nose. The answers to our most harrowing questions have always been within us. This fact has been told, written and repeated countless times over the centuries but we have been too preoccupied to understand this simple fact.

realm of a profound science waiting to be discovered. All the absurd, fantastical stories and specific weird details contained within scriptures like Brahma sitting on a lotus, and the earth being on the tusk of a boar, etc. are not there merely as a testimony of human imagination and creativity but also of the deep understanding of the nature of the human body(internal) and the external world. I am sure that the people reading this journal are aware that in spite of the present conditions in the advancements in the field of science we have not made any significant progress in actually answering the real questions i.e. how this universe came into being, why? Why do we evolve? What is time? Why am I alive? To answer these questions Science has to widen its perspectives. A true scientist is one who knows that magic and science are the same thing, a Yogi believes and understands this. It is time we left behind our preconceived notions of science, of reality and widen our perspectives to truly understand this wonderful gift of life that we have been given, to change ourselves for better. It is time we learnt to be kind, to be grateful for this experience of human life, to look within ourselves and reach the highest truth of being.

Science hidden in Bible, Lord Jesus and his magic, Biblical monuments, Revelations, Plato's world, the reason for the creation of ancient monuments and their implications, Heaven, and the pathway to Heaven have all been explained in another article.

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